

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Dimethylformamide by Periodate in Alkaline Medium

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Ruthenium(III) catalyses the oxidation of DMF by IO_4^- in aqueous alkaline medium. The reaction is zero order in $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ and a Ru^{III} catalytic cycle is indicated. The pre-equilibrium adduct between $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ and DMF suffers slow intermolecular decomposition to Ru^{I} and oxidation products of DMF, Ru^{III} is then regenerated by IO_4^- in a fast step. The reaction constants involved in the mechanism are derived.

The use of ruthenium(III) as a catalyst is of recent interest¹ in view of the possibility of variety of mechanisms and various oxidation states of ruthenium. In acid medium with different oxidants² DMF decomposes to give formic acid and dimethylamine (DMA). DMA does not react further and oxidation of formic acid is essentially the only reaction in acid medium. However, in alkaline medium, formic acid is unaffected whereas DMA undergoes oxidation.

DMF oxidation of periodate is very slow in both acid and alkaline media. Ruthenium(III) does not catalyse the reaction in acid medium but pronounced catalysis is observed in alkaline medium. We have investigated the kinetics of the process.

Results and Discussion

The reaction order was determined from the slope of log (initial rate) versus log (concentration) plots. The reaction was carried out varying the concentrations of oxidant, reductant, catalyst and alkali in turn while keeping all other conditions constant (Table 1). Under such conditions the orders found in [DMF] and $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ are less than unity and unity respectively. The initial rates were found to be independent of the initial concentration of the oxidant and the concentration versus time plots were linear and parallel which indicates zero order in [oxidant]. The slopes of concentration versus time plots were taken as zero order rate constants (k_0) of the reaction and they were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. The rate constants increased with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 1).

Added reaction products, viz. iodate, formate and ammonia did not have any significant effect on the reaction, whilst the ionic strength had a marginal effect on the rate. The effect of solvent polarity on the reaction was studied by varying the t-BuOH content in the reaction mixture. The rate increased with the decrease in polarity of the solvent. The dielectric constants used were computed from the values of the pure liquids as in earlier work³. The solvent does not react with the oxidant under the experimental conditions. Kinetic runs at temperatures 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45° ($[\text{IO}_4^-] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{DMF}] = 0.1$, $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-6}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.02$ and $I = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) resulted the zero order rate constants as 4.5×10^{-6} , 6.8×10^{-6} , 8.7×10^{-6} , 12.6×10^{-6}

and $17.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. Using these data, activation parameters were calculated to be as $E_a = 51.7 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -182 \pm 7 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. For the uncatalysed reaction under similar conditions E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be $76 \pm 3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-498 \pm 20 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[\text{IO}_4^-]$, [DMF], $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ AND $[\text{OH}^-]$ ON THE Ru^{III} CATALYSED PERIODATE OXIDATION DMF IN AQUEOUS ALKALINE MEDIUM

Temp. = 25°, $I = 0.025 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$					
$10^3 [\text{IO}_4^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10 [\text{DMF}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^6 [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^2 [\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^6 k_0 (\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1})$	
				Exptl.	Calcd.*
1.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.2	4.3
2.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	4.3
3.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.4	4.3
4.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.3	4.3
6.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.1	4.3
10.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.4	4.3
4.0	0.5	5.0	2.0	2.6	2.4
4.0	0.7	5.0	2.0	3.4	3.3
4.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	4.3
4.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	7.2	7.4
4.0	3.0	5.0	2.0	10	9.7
4.0	5.0	5.0	2.0	14	13
4.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	0.87
4.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	1.9	1.7
4.0	1.0	3.0	2.0	2.5	2.6
4.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.5	4.3
4.0	1.0	7.0	2.0	5.9	6.1
4.0	1.0	10	2.0	8.8	8.7
$I = 0.085 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$					
4.0	1.0	5.0	0.8	2.2	2.2
4.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	2.6	2.6
4.0	1.0	5.0	2.0	4.2	4.3
4.0	1.0	5.0	3.0	5.5	5.6
4.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	7.1	7.2
4.0	1.0	5.0	8.0	9.2	8.6

*Zero order rate constants were calculated using the values of k , K_1 and K_2 as $5.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $13.3 \pm 0.6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $10.0 \pm 0.4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Error $\pm 4\%$.

The spectra of Ru^{III} in alkaline medium is different as compared to the aqueous neutral medium and it is also observed that absorbance of Ru^{III} increases with increase in [OH⁻] and finally remains constant. This indicates the predominance of one species of Ru^{III} presumably [Ru(H₂O)₅OH]²⁺. Because of this reason and the fact that initial rate is a function of [OH⁻], with fractional order in [OH⁻], the main Ru^{III} species is likely to be [Ru(H₂O)₅OH]²⁺ and its formation in equilibrium (1) is of importance in the reaction. This conclusion is in agreement with earlier work^{1,4}.

The results suggest the formation of an adduct between DMF and the hydroxy species of Ru^{III}. Similar adduct formation was observed in earlier study^{5,6} and that is evidenced by the fractional order found in [DMF]. However, attempts to obtain spectral evidence for the intermediate adduct were in vain. Scheme 1 apparently explains the kinetic observations.

Transient Ru^I species is reconverted to Ru^{III} by oxidant. However, in view of the very low concentration of Ru^{III} used, no kinetic evidence could be obtained for the formation of Ru^I. The Ru^I formation is also in accordance with the earlier works⁷. The probable structure of the adduct (A) may be as given below,

Adduct (A)

Assuming $K_1[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \ll 1$ and also $K_2[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] \ll 1$, the rate equation derived for Scheme 1 is

$$-\frac{d[\text{IO}_4^-]}{dt} = \text{Rate} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{DMF}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{OH}^-]}{1 + K_1 [\text{OH}^-] + K_1 K_2 [\text{DMF}] [\text{OH}^-]} \quad (2)$$

which satisfactorily explains all the observed kinetic features.

According to equation (2), plots of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}/\text{rate}$ versus $[\text{OH}^-]^{-1}$ and $[\text{DMF}]^{-1}$ should be linear and are found to be so. From the slopes and intercepts of such plots the values of k , K_1 and K_2 at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ were calculated to be $5.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $13.3 \pm 0.6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $10.0 \pm 0.4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respective-

ly. Using these values, the zero order rate constants over a range of conditions were calculated and compared with the experimental values in Table 1. There is a good agreement between them.

The negligibly small effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate is consistent with a reaction between neutral and charged species (Scheme 1). The effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate is also as expected for a reaction between an ion and a neutral molecule⁸. The activation energy calculated for Ru^{III}-catalysed reaction was found to be much smaller compared to the uncatalysed process which explains the catalytic effect (see *infra*).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The stock solution of IO_4^- were prepared by dissolving KIO_4 (Riedel) and used after keeping 24 h. It was standardised iodometrically⁹. DMF (Sisco) was distilled under reduced pressure¹⁰ and its stock solution prepared by appropriate dilution with water. Ruthenium(III) solutions were made by dissolving RuCl_3 (Sd. Fine) in $0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HCl}$; the concentration was ascertained by EDTA titration¹¹. The IO_3^- solution was prepared by dissolving KIO_3 (Rechem) in H_2O . NaClO_4 and NaOH were used to maintain ionic strength and alkalinity constant respectively.

Kinetic runs : The reaction solutions were prepared by mixing the previously thermostated reactant solutions of IO_4^- , Ru^{III} and DMF, which contained the required amounts of NaOH and NaClO_4 . Aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at regular intervals of time and poured into an iodine flask containing distilled water and sufficient KH_2PO_4 to just neutralise the alkali and to bring the pH of resulting solution to 5.0–5.5. The liberated I_2 was titrated⁹ against standard $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ using starch as an indicator. Under these conditions, IO_3^- was without any effect on the added I^- , and the IO_4^- was quantitatively reduced to IO_3^- .

At room temperature and at higher temperature, in alkaline medium, the DMF was not hydrolysed to any significant extent. Kinetic runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with [DMF] nearly ten-fold excess over [oxidant] at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Initial rates were determined by the plane-mirror method¹² and were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry : Different reaction mixtures containing excess $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ over [DMF] with constant $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$ (5.0×10^{-6} and 0.02 mol dm^{-3} respectively) were kept for over 24 h at 25° and then analysed. The remaining IO_4^- was assayed iodometrically as mentioned earlier. Other products, HCO_2^- and NH_3 were identified by spot test¹³ and Nessler's reagent test¹¹ respectively, as the main products. There was no perceptible reaction between IO_4^- and HCO_2^-

in alkaline medium. The results show 1 : 4 stoichiometry as shown below,

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